

Data for Policy Conference 2022

**Trust-Enabled Data Technology in Smart City:
Comparing the COVID-19 Contact Tracing App of
Hong Kong and Singapore**

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Keywords:

Contact Tracing, Trust, Data Governance, Digital Governance, Smart City, COVID-19, Hong Kong, Singapore

Oct 2022

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UPDATED Abstract

This paper examines the importance of trust building to data-driven technology and innovation in smart city by comparing the two contrasting cases of Hong Kong and Singapore in their adoption and outcomes of using digital technologies for combatting the COVID-19 pandemic. Using the LeaveHomeSafe app of Hong Kong and the TraceTogether app of Singapore as a case study, it applies and extends the theoretical framework of human trust in technology to explain citizen resistance or acceptance to the app, a state-dominated technology, which can vary according to contexts based on trust in both the technology and the government.

Trust plays a critical role in the effectiveness of public policies (OECD 2017) including the development of smart city as smart city is not only about technology but also people and their acceptance and engagement with technologies (Albino et al. 2015; Cowley et al. 2018; Joss et al. 2019; Vanolo, 2016). Smart city is essentially a data-driven city relying heavily on data provided by citizens via ubiquitous devices to produce seamlessly connected services. But technologies is never adopted in a contextless vacuum without the human and social dimension and its adoption is an inherently social, developmental and manageable process. Technology acceptance is a social process and a technology must be socially accepted in order to exist, function and impact (Lederer et al. 2000; Rauniar et al. 2014). This does not mean to downplay the significance of the technical aspect of a technology but it is becoming increasingly clear that simply better technology and more data would not automatically self-transform into effective solutions if concerns and issues of citizens on major issues such as privacy, transparency and accountability are not addressed (van Zoonen, 2016).

In essence, with its heavy reliance on citizen-generated data, many smart city technologies are trust-enabled technologies, meaning only with sufficient and good-quality data provided by citizens in a trustworthy manner that the technologies can function properly. Data are its fuel and lifeline as all its decisions are intensively data-based (Jacobs et al. 2020; Schintler and Kulkarni 2014; van Zoonen 2020) and trust ensures the cooperation of citizens in data provision. All smart functions are supported by intelligent exchanges of information flowing between its many different subsystem covering various types of products and services relevant to urban functions. In a smart city, it is a daily routine to see massive amount of different types of data including citizen data collected from multiple sources for a wide variety of purposes (Joss et al. 2019).

The cases of contact tracing app in Hong Kong and Singapore serve as a useful comparative case to highlight the importance of citizen trust in enabling smart city data-driven innovation. A main research question of this study is the relationship between trust building and data-driven innovation in smart city from the perspective of the adoption of the contact tracing app by the citizens in the two city-states. The full functioning of smart city data-driven technologies involves more than just the data itself but also the human and social dimension including data trust and governance (Kariotis et al. 2020; Stalla-Bourdillon et al. 2020; van Zoonen 2020). As Fountain (2001) argues in her seminal work on “technology enactment framework,” technological advancement and adoption and its impact on institutional change is a complex and interactive process that is never cast by technological forces alone. The impact of information technology on institutional and societal changes depends on how the related

technologies are perceived by the institutional actors such as how their goals and interests are affected (Welch and Wong 2001).

Case study is a legitimate and well-accepted method commonly used for small-N analysis when there is not enough observations for quantitative analysis (Van Evera 1997). Due to the richness of its information collected, it is a useful tool allowing both theory testing and theory development (George and Bennett 2005). Although case study is mainly a strategy of qualitative research, similar to quantitative research, the same logic of scientific inference is applied (King, Koehane and Verba 1994). As a major strength of qualitative research is its ability to answer the questions of “why” and “how” with the consideration of contexts and human experience, it is a research strategy suitable for the purpose of this study in understanding technology acceptance and app resistance from the citizen perspective.

This study follows the case study principles proposed by Yin (2013). They include the use of multiple sources of evidence, using both qualitative and quantitative data, and a chain of evidence linked explicitly between the research questions, the theory and the conclusion. The sources of evidence collected and analysed consist of government documents and its websites. Other sources include content of media reports including social media such as YouTube, direct and participant observation, and analysis of survey findings by university and research institutes. For the principle of creating a chain of evidence, one of the main tasks of the analysis of government documents and media reports is to construct a timeline of major events for utilizing the approach of process tracing. Process tracing is a method for within-case analysis to enhance the level of causal inference in a case study (Morgan 2016). It can strengthen the causal analysis of a case study by confirming that the major events in the case study are consistent with the explanation and propositions of the theoretical framework under examination (Collier 2011).

With multiple sources of evidence and a process tracing approach, it examines how smart city data-driven technology is accepted or resisted by citizens due to level of attention to the 4Ps (performance, process, purpose, and protection) of trust in technology in Hong Kong and Singapore. It represents a good opportunity of applying and further developing the theoretical framework and identifying the factors and strategies of trust building to generate insights and lessons on important topics such as data governance, institutional trust, and data trust in smart cities.

In the study, we find technology adoption is a social process but unfortunately this social dimension is not realized in the case of the COVID contact tracing, especially in Hong Kong. The old paradigm of limiting the technology projects to experts is outdated and inappropriate. Concerns of all four dimensions of trust should be addressed. Trust can be enhanced through better data governance such as producing more public engagement and strengthening the accountability system. Interestingly, trust (mistrust) can be transferrable. As shown in Singapore, trust in institutions can at least partly substitute for trust in technology. There is growing amount of literature concerning the “dark side” of smart city and technology. Without addressing the concerns and issues behind the app / technology hesitancy including the trust issue, it is unclear its mandatory adoption can really lead to an improvement of the app performance in combatting COVID-19. There will be concerns on data quality as citizens can adopt their own counter measures to circumvent the new policy and defeat the original objective of contact tracing / data-enable technologies. Importantly, it also defeats the original purpose of smart city – serving the citizens.